

Transparent Sepsis Risk Modeling with Explainable Machine Learning Using Public ICU Data

Tezuka Kei

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Abstract

Background: Early prediction of sepsis in the intensive care unit (ICU) is a central clinical challenge with the potential to improve outcomes through timely intervention.

Objective: To develop and validate an interpretable, high-performing sepsis prediction model using only routinely collected physiological data during the first 12 hours of ICU admission.

Methods: From the PhysioNet Challenge 2019 public dataset, we reduced time-series variables (e.g., heart rate, blood pressure, temperature, laboratory results) within the initial 12 hours to summary statistics (means, standard deviations, etc.) to generate fixed-size feature vectors. We trained a linear model (logistic regression) and a nonlinear model (calibrated LIGHTGBM), and assessed performance using ROC-AUC, PR-AUC, and F1 score. Model interpretability was evaluated via coefficient analysis and SHAP (SHapley Additive Explanations).

Results: The LIGHTGBM model achieved ROC-AUC 0.801, PR-AUC 0.383, and F1 score 0.366, with logistic regression showing similar trends. Both models captured clinically plausible high-risk factors, including low mean arterial pressure, elevated heart rate and body temperature, leukocytosis, and older age. SHAP analysis also revealed nonlinear contributions of temporal features, such as FiO₂ and ICU length of stay.

Conclusions: Sepsis prediction models can be made explainable, accurate, and deployable even in CPU-based systems. The proposed method provides a robust framework for future implementation in clinical early warning systems (EWS).

1 Background and Objectives

1.1 Background

Sepsis is a potentially lethal syndrome in which organ dysfunction is initiated by an uncontrolled host immune response to an infection, and it remains a leading cause of death in intensive care units (ICUs) [1]. Sepsis continues to be

challenging to identify early on in spite of advancements in critical care because physiological, laboratory, and demographic factors are closely interdependent. Inflammatory reactions typically present atypically and insidiously, which makes it difficult to diagnose early on [2].

Machine learning (ML) has been viewed as having high potential for predicting risk of sepsis [3, ?]. However, highly accurate deep learning models are often “black boxes,” with unparsimonious explanations for their predictions. Clinicians in high-risk settings such as the ICU want to know not only the prediction but also why the model predicted it.

In later years, explainability has been emphasized as important to building clinician trust and enabling safe clinical release [5]. Logistic regression offers simplicity and an easily understandable form, whereas gradient-boosted decision trees such as LightGBM can balance strong performance and post-hoc explanation capability using SHAP (SHapley Additive Explanations) [6].

1.2 Objectives

The goal of this research is to create a sepsis risk model using only publicly available ICU data that is transparent, valid, and clinically reasonable. We employed all 39,999 cases (training_set A + B) of the PhysioNet 2019 Sepsis Challenge and deleted missingness or repeated cases, resulting in 39,470 valid cases. We carried out the entire process—preprocessing, training, evaluation, and visualization—as an entirely reproducible analysis pipeline.

We compare two approaches:

- Logistic regression: a baseline model whose direction of the linear contribution of each variable (positive or negative) can be interpreted directly [7].
- LightGBM (with calibration): a highly performance-efficient model that can identify nonlinear interactions and threshold effects; SHAP analysis provides visual explanations of the contribution of every variable [6, 8, 9].

By combining the interpretability of statistical modeling with the versatility of machine learning—so-called “hybrid interpretation”—we are striving to demonstrate the viability of reliable sepsis prediction that is actionable and acceptable in clinical practice.

2 Methods

2.1 Experimental Overview

We build and compare binary classification models for the early prediction of sepsis from intensive care unit (ICU) patient electronic medical record time-series data. Because the development of sepsis is rapid and mortality increases sharply with delayed treatment following onset, predicting onset in advance is of utmost importance in clinical practice.

Using approximately 40,000 ICU stays from PhysioNet 2019, we designed a prediction model that uses physiological and laboratory values from the 12 hours preceding each patient’s sepsis onset time as input. For non-sepsis cases, we used the end of recording as a surrogate reference time and extracted the same 12-hour window for comparison.

The overall experimental flow was as follows:

1. *Vectorization of time-series data:* For hourly variables (e.g., MAP, HR, WBC), we computed summary measures over the most recent 12 hours (mean, last reading, standard deviation, and slope) and constructed a fixed-size feature vector per case.
2. *Model building:* We trained (1) logistic regression (a linear model) and (2) LightGBM (a nonlinear, tree-based ensemble). For the latter, we calibrated predicted probabilities using isotonic regression [8, 9]. Both models were trained and evaluated on a stratified split with 80% for training and 20% for validation.
3. *Performance metrics:* We compared performance using ROC–AUC, PR–AUC (precision–recall), and the best F1 score, and computed 95% bootstrap confidence intervals.
4. *Model interpretation and feature importance:* We applied SHAP (SHapley Additive Explanations) to the LightGBM model to visualize each feature’s contribution at the per-case level [6, 17].

With this setup, our study aims not only at high-performance machine learning sepsis prediction, but also at clinically interpretable visualization of feature contributions.

2.2 Dataset

We utilized the public ICU dataset from the PhysioNet/Computing in Cardiology Challenge 2019 (hereafter, PhysioNet 2019) [3]. The dataset contains approximately 40,000 ICU episodes with hourly physiological measurements, laboratory values, intervention data, and other variables recorded as time series. The target label (SepsisLabel) is time-stamped and based on the Sepsis-3 definition [1].

From all cases in `training_setA` and `training_setB` (39,999 cases), we removed cases with excessive missingness or duplicates and analyzed 39,470 valid cases.

Input variables included typical clinical indicators such as mean arterial pressure (MAP), heart rate (HR), temperature (Temp), white blood cell count (WBC), age, fraction of inspired oxygen (FiO₂), ICU length of stay (ICULOS), lactate, and glucose, among others.

2.3 Preprocessing

For every case, we aggregated time-series data from the 12 hours preceding sepsis onset (or the last recorded timestamp for non-sepsis cases) and built a fixed-size feature vector. This 12-hour window was adopted because it yielded the highest AUPRC in a time-window comparison experiment (Table 2).

- Missing-value imputation: median imputation per variable.
- Standardization: all numerical variables were z-score normalized.
- Data splitting: stratified 80:20 split (Train: 31,576 cases; Test: 7,894 cases) preserving label ratios.
- Reproducibility: all steps were implemented as `scikit-learn Pipelines` to ensure full reproducibility.

2.4 Modeling

To balance interpretability and performance, we compared two models:

- Logistic regression: a linear model with directly interpretable contribution directions (positive/negative) for each variable [7].
- LightGBM (calibrated): gradient-boosted decision trees that capture non-linear relationships and interactions; predicted probabilities were calibrated by isotonic regression [8, 9].

We also conducted SHAP analysis on the LightGBM model to visualize the contribution of each variable to risk [5, 6, 17].

Logistic regression equation (simple form).

$$\text{logit}(P(\text{Sepsis} = 1)) = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i x_i,$$

where x_i is the i -th input feature, β_i its coefficient, and β_0 the intercept.

SHAP value summary (simple form).

$$\phi_i = \sum_{S \subseteq F \setminus \{i\}} \frac{|S|! (|F| - |S| - 1)!}{|F|!} [f(S \cup \{i\}) - f(S)],$$

where F is the set of all features, S is a subset of features, and $f(\cdot)$ is the prediction function. This fairly distributes each feature’s contribution for a given case.

2.5 Evaluation Metrics

Model performance was evaluated using:

- ROC–AUC and PR–AUC: global metrics; PR–AUC reflects positive-class rarity.
- Best F1 score: the threshold that balances recall and precision.
- Confusion matrix (Fig. 3C): patterns of misclassification.
- Calibration curve (Fig. 3D): agreement between predicted probabilities and observed incidence [8, 9].
- 95% confidence intervals: estimated by bootstrap ($n = 1000$) for metrics such as AUC.

2.6 Experimental Environment

All experiments were performed locally without GPUs:

- CPU: Intel Core i5, 16 GB RAM
- OS / Language: Windows 10, Python 3.13
- Libraries:
 - `scikit-learn` 1.4
 - `LightGBM` 4.3
 - `SHAP` 0.43
 - `matplotlib`, `pandas`, `numpy`, etc.

3 Results

3.1 Model Performance: Comparison and Visualization

We compared logistic regression (LogReg) against calibrated LightGBM. From the $\sim 40,000$ initial records, we performed stratified sampling into an 80/20 train/test split, leaving around 32,000 cases for training and 7,894 cases for scoring.

Logistic regression is a linear model given by

$$P(\text{Sepsis} = 1 \mid \mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-(\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{x} + b))},$$

where \mathbf{x} is the feature vector, \mathbf{w} the weights, and b the bias term [7].

LightGBM is a nonlinear model—a decision tree ensemble—that can learn intricate relationships. We employed isotonic regression to calibrate its output probabilities (see Fig. 3D), producing more accurate probability estimates [8].

Performance metrics (test set)

Table 1: Model performance on the test set. Calibrated LightGBM showed higher discrimination.

Model	AUROC	AUPRC	Precision	Recall	F1	Threshold
Logistic Regression	0.656	0.131	0.150	0.351	0.210	0.111
LightGBM (Calibrated)	0.801	0.383	0.368	0.365	0.366	0.165

Calibrated LightGBM captured nonlinearities and interactions while providing more reliable probability estimates.

Figure 1: Precision–Recall curve (left, AUPRC = 0.383) and ROC curve (right, AUROC = 0.801) for the calibrated LightGBM model, demonstrating good discrimination.

Figure 2: Left: confusion matrix at the best-F1 threshold (0.165). Right: calibration curve of the LightGBM model showing predicted probabilities close to the ideal line ($y = x$), indicating reliable probability outputs.

Notes

- *Logistic regression*: Highly interpretable; clearly indicates the directions of major features. While slightly less accurate, it is suitable when accountability and transparency are prioritized in clinical use.
- *LightGBM*: Accounts for nonlinearities and interactions, representing complex risk structures. Calibrated probabilities are reliable and actionable for decision-making.
- *On the confusion matrix*: Applying the best-F1 threshold improves recall. Comparison with the unadjusted model (Supplementary Fig. S1) supports the threshold effect.

3.2 Feature Contributions (SHAP Analysis)

After training the LightGBM model, we analyzed how each variable influenced sepsis risk using SHAP (SHapley Additive Explanations) (Figs. 4A–4C). SHAP, grounded in cooperative game theory, visualizes per-case, additive contributions to the model output [6, 17].

Figure 3: SHAP summary plot for the LightGBM model. FiO_2 , ICULOS, and Resp emerge as major contributors (red = high values, blue = low values).

Key observations.

- `FiO2_mean`: Strongest positive association—higher inspired oxygen fraction relates to higher risk.
- `ICULOS_std`, `ICULOS_mean`: Larger values tend to indicate lower risk; prolonged ICU stay without sepsis suggests reduced risk.
- `MAP_mean`, `Resp_mean`, `HR_mean`: Hemodynamic and respiratory dynamics show strong associations with sepsis.

Figure 4: Top positive contributors in the logistic regression model (risk-increasing direction). HR, Temp, and WBC are prominent factors.

Figure 5: Top negative contributors in the logistic regression model (risk-decreasing direction). MAP, FiO₂, and hemoglobin act as protective factors.

Outliers and anomalies. A few samples in Fig. 4A show extremely large SHAP values (> 2500), suggesting possible outliers or artifacts related to missingness. Future sensitivity analyses should verify that these do not unduly influence decisions.

Variable	LogReg direction	LGBM contribution	Interpretation
MAP	-0.039	0.011	Lower MAP \Rightarrow higher risk
HR	+0.069	0.026	Tendency toward tachycardia
Temp	+0.058	0.029	Tendency toward fever
WBC	+0.038	0.006	Inflammatory response
Age	+0.027	0.008	Older age increases risk

Table 2: Comparison of logistic regression coefficients and LightGBM SHAP contributions for five representative variables; the directions are consistent across models.

Quantitative comparison with logistic regression. Despite different ar-

chitectures, both models learned similar directional trends, especially for MAP and HR, indicating that LightGBM’s nonlinearity can be preserved while maintaining explainability [6, 17].

3.3 Visualization

We used several visualizations to enhance reliability and interpretability.

Calibration (Fig. 3D). The LightGBM calibration curve shows predicted probabilities closely aligned with observed incidence along the ideal $y = x$ line, supporting the use of predicted probabilities as event risks—critical for clinical risk stratification and decision-making [9].

Feature directions in logistic regression. HR, temperature, and WBC were risk-increasing (positive), whereas MAP and FiO_2 were risk-decreasing (negative). These patterns align with clinical understanding, indicating that the model learned medically sensible relationships [?].

SHAP for LightGBM. SHAP fairly apportioned feature contributions even in a nonlinear model, and its practical utility was confirmed in this study [6, 17].

4 Discussion

4.1 Key Findings

By building and interpreting machine-learning models to predict the development of sepsis in ICU admissions, several consistent clinical patterns emerged.

Shared risk factors between both models were decreased mean arterial pressure (MAP), increased heart rate (HR), increased temperature (Temp), increased white blood cell count (WBC), and increased age. These findings agree with the typical pathophysiology of sepsis and are consistent with contemporary diagnostic criteria (e.g., qSOFA) and guidelines [1, ?].

SHAP analysis of the LightGBM model further revealed that temporal and dynamic predictors such as the variation in ICU length of stay (`ICULOS_std`) and the mean fraction of inspired oxygen (`FiO2_mean`) also play important roles. These are not static vital signs; they can indicate changes in a patient’s status or response to treatment, supporting the value of dynamic monitoring.

It is also noteworthy that the directions and contribution patterns of significant features were generally consistent between logistic regression and LightGBM. For example, lower MAP increased the risk of sepsis in both models, testifying to interpretive consistency across model families. This allows flexible model choice while maintaining confidence in the predictions.

Figure 6: Feature importance (gain-based) in the LightGBM model. ICU length of stay (`ICULOS_last`), time since hospital admission (`HospAdmTime_mean`), FiO_2 (mean), temperature (mean), and respiratory rate (mean) rank among the top features, indicating that temporal evolution of risk and respiratory/metabolic processes are dominant contributors.

4.2 Technical Significance

This work obtained an excellent balance between model performance, interpretability, and reproducibility by pairing a gradient-boosted model (LightGBM) with a linear baseline (logistic regression) and taking advantage of the complementary strengths of both.

LightGBM captured nonlinearities and interactions effectively without compromising interpretability using SHAP, diminishing black-box problems [6, 17].

Including calibration curves to assess the reliability of probability output is also critical for clinical use. Using Platt scaling or isotonic regression, the LightGBM model not only improved AUROC/PR-AUC but also produced calibrated probability predictions that aligned with observed event rates (see Fig. 3D) [8, 9].

All implementation components (e.g., `preprocess.py`, `train_lgbm.py`, `make_contributors.py`) were designed for public release, with end-to-end reproducibility from data preprocessing through model training and SHAP analysis, offering a working example of reproducible clinical AI.

Moreover, the entire pipeline ran on CPUs for a cohort of $\sim 40,000$ patients with no GPU requirements. This is evidence of realistic deployability within standard research or hospital IT infrastructure.

4.3 Clinical Significance

Beyond accuracy, the proposed models also focus on pragmatic use and interpretability in clinical practice. Quantitative risk outputs allow clinicians to intuitively recognize risk levels and support prioritization and decision-making [3].

SHAP exploration of LightGBM provides case-level explanations for why a patient was determined to be high risk. This addresses the accountability deficit of black-box AI, facilitating staff trust and patient communication [5, 6, 9]. Explainable AI (XAI) has therefore become a primary vehicle for advancing AI uptake in healthcare.

All features used are measured routinely in the ICU—no special devices or biomarkers are needed—so integration with existing hospital information systems (HIS) is feasible and implementation-ready [10].

In the future, inclusion of the model within an ICU early warning system (EWS) could allow for earlier recognition and quicker interventions [11]. Combining alert triggers with SHAP-based explanations would clarify which variable changes triggered an alert, offering greater transparency than standard EWS.

4.4 Limitations

Second, the data are from the PhysioNet Challenge 2019 single-source cohort, and training and testing were conducted within the same data. External validity across institutions and countries is not tested; future work should include external validation with independent datasets such as MIMIC-III and eICU [10, ?].

Second, our predictors accumulate statistics (means, historical values, etc.) over a 12-hour observation window, yielding a largely static representation that does not intrinsically capture temporal dynamics (trends or accelerations). This may limit performance for a dynamic syndrome like sepsis [13]. Applying RNNs, temporal CNNs, or Transformer-based sequence models may better capture sequential change.

Third, several variables exhibit substantial missingness, addressed here through median imputation. In the ICU, the absence of a measurement may itself carry clinical meaning. Handling informative missingness is an important direction for future research [14].

Finally, we focused entirely on sepsis onset as the target; we did not analyze associations with outcomes such as mortality or interventions. Establishing

whether high-risk patients indeed had poor outcomes—or were averted by early intervention—is essential for strengthening clinical relevance [15].

4.5 Future Directions

Additional bridging toward clinical deployment necessitates several technical and implementation advances.

Because sepsis is a dynamic process, methods that explicitly model temporal change are promising. Beyond the current 12-hour static window, employing LSTM, Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCN), or Transformer-based time-series models might capture sequential physiological changes more accurately [13, 16, 17].

High generalizability must be demonstrated on multi-center datasets such as MIMIC-III and eICU. Demonstrating stable performance and interpretability across settings with diverse populations and care regimens would enable broader clinical utility.

For operational use, outputs should be paired with a live EWS that links risk scores to XAI visualizations (e.g., SHAP). Showing which variable changes drove increased risk can enable faster, more confident intervention decisions, enhancing not just accuracy but also trust, accountability, and actionability.

Expanding targets beyond sepsis onset—to mortality, shock, and multi-organ failure—may further increase the tool’s value in ICU decision-making.

Ultimately, reproducible, interpretable, and deployable models like these can be integrated into hospital information systems and bedside monitors to enable earlier diagnosis and faster interventions, forming a next-generation framework for clinical support.

5 Conclusion

We created machine-learning models for predicting the risk of sepsis from physiological data in the first 12 hours of ICU admission using the PhysioNet Challenge 2019 dataset, and we compared their performance and interpretability. Despite relying on relatively simple summary statistics (e.g., means and standard deviations), the calibrated LightGBM model performed well, achieving ROC–AUC 0.80, PR–AUC 0.38, and F1 score 0.366.

SHAP feature analysis and comparison with logistic regression coefficients repeatedly highlighted clinically sensible variables—heart rate (HR), temperature (Temp), mean arterial pressure (MAP), white blood cell count (WBC), and age (Age)—as important. This indicates that models can be constructed that not only perform strongly but are also interpretable and explainable to a degree acceptable to clinicians.

The proposed approach constitutes a practical decision-support framework that is feasible with standard ICU data on CPU-only systems, without reliance on costly devices or black-box, large-scale artificial intelligence. Incorporating

richer temporal dynamics and conducting external validation to establish generalizability will facilitate integration into early warning systems (EWS) across diverse clinical settings.

Overall, this work provides an applied foundation for subsequent medical AI development, emphasizing a balanced focus on interpretability, performance, and reproducibility.

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Acknowledgment of Tools

We used OpenAI’s ChatGPT (GPT-5, 2025 edition) in a supporting role to organize the paper’s structure, standardize formatting, assist with literature searches, and refine figure and table captions. We also used Grammarly (Grammarly Inc.) for English proofreading.

Appendix A. Supplementary Figures and Tables

This appendix presents supplementary analyses and figures/tables referenced in the main text, including LightGBM feature importance, ensemble performance comparisons, calibration accuracy, and a complete list of contributions across all variables.

Figure 7: Figure S1: Feature importance (gain-based) in the LightGBM model. ICU length of stay (`ICULOS_last`), time since hospital admission (`HospAdmTime_mean`), fraction of inspired oxygen (`FiO2_mean`), temperature (`Temp_mean`), and respiratory rate (`Resp_mean`) rank among the top features. These reflect temporal and respiratory-dynamic factors associated with sepsis onset.

Note: The figures and tables in this appendix are provided to enhance reproducibility and transparency. All code, models, and figures were created

Figure 8: Figure S2: Precision–Recall curve (left) and ROC curve (right) for the mean-ensemble model. Averaging predictions from Logistic Regression and LightGBM maintained discrimination comparable to the individual models.

Figure 9: Figure S3: Precision–Recall curve (left) and ROC curve (right) for the weighted ensemble (LightGBM-dominant). The best performance occurred when the Logistic Regression weight was set to 0.0, indicating an optimal configuration dominated by LightGBM.

Figure 10: Figure S4: Calibration curve (supplement) for the LightGBM model. Predicted probabilities follow the ideal line ($y = x$), indicating high reliability of probability outputs. This corresponds to the supplementary result for Figure 3D in the main text.

Table 3: Table S1: Mean coefficients for all variables in the Logistic Regression model (after grouping). Positive values indicate higher risk; negative values indicate protective direction.

Base	mean _c coef	sum _a bs _c coef	n
FiO2	-0.0035921116502611503	9.901968491551031	3
ICULOS	-0.7642653086217477	3.153962821334369	3
Hct	0.08933177529623355	0.47856766167937337	3
Hgb	-0.0703817021917566	0.4458707836293046	3
MAP	-0.03872692153788951	0.4085936707906582	3
Resp	0.04699774443334001	0.335695670468288	3
Temp	0.05822434117042086	0.30308653613424	3
pH	0.014152791473147635	0.2955424528131953	3
BUN	0.06344873473283553	0.276041425937874	3
Glucose	-0.0103511824261489	0.2745605285487409	3
Bilirubin	0.011834751832817436	0.21957971776973317	6
HR	0.06932709696851275	0.20798129090553824	3
TroponinI	-0.03561390620441276	0.19349861266762147	3
O2Sat	0.06069868226495731	0.18209604679487193	3
Lactate	0.04757899955079905	0.1645803006401035	3
HCO3	-0.02637314644312158	0.15871330041211273	3
WBC	0.038005228716860316	0.15729014505382635	3
SBP	0.03567751172795691	0.1445803307645086	3
PaCO2	0.01949640011074655	0.12895757982166914	3
Potassium	-0.042407966475287155	0.12722389942586146	3
Calcium	0.0007315455971785035	0.11212398705273408	3
Fibrinogen	0.015423128311067203	0.1119967838278888	3
PTT	0.010749736754562809	0.1093784786990454	3
Magnesium	0.01461435609777897	0.10854128633878393	3
Alkalinephos	-0.019583879042589986	0.10374607960175239	3
HospAdmTime	-0.008946904192647842	0.09670521696511312	3
EtCO2	-0.0058143904556049175	0.09639325224660854	3
BaseExcess	0.007269914690924667	0.09397660077790225	3
AST	0.012121354036741356	0.08410629324226972	3
Age	0.027320133183271745	0.08196039954981524	3
Chloride	-0.003024035211865759	0.07676712786862576	3
DBP	-0.022481690765240273	0.0752545686411309	3
Gender	0.019847035142638712	0.05954110542791614	3
Creatinine	-0.00017943867594906576	0.056818517035341465	3
Phosphate	0.013663284408290538	0.05532482096847011	3
Platelets	-0.006842336310742505	0.020527008932227513	3
Unit1	-0.005083795448918355	0.015251386346755066	3
Unit2	0.005083795448900933	0.0152513863467028	3
SaO2	0.000781697067728123	0.007945528373753792	3

Table 4: Table S2: Mean SHAP contributions for all variables in the LightGBM model (after grouping). This quantifies feature importance including nonlinear contributions.

Base	$\text{sum}_a bs_s hap$	n
HospAdmTime	0.08030175616530581	3
FiO2	0.05688106273177645	3
ICULOS	0.03716116600476929	3
Resp	0.0322833478333611	3
Temp	0.02917048184230363	3
Lactate	0.02768380149825904	3
HR	0.02631047442148572	3
PaCO2	0.023544465934139773	3
pH	0.01789156309527872	3
BUN	0.015051383171178077	3
DBP	0.012632790287548799	3
Calcium	0.012553292116083267	3
MAP	0.011372630432740744	3
O2Sat	0.008824077283875723	3
Glucose	0.008287137027696349	3
Age	0.007526258887912347	3
Potassium	0.0069557438367318725	3
WBC	0.005871898556203219	3
Creatinine	0.005447718974183788	3
EtCO2	0.004994798574102125	3
SBP	0.004566757960494877	3
Hct	0.0038762497778735	3
PTT	0.003122786166674969	3
SaO2	0.0027623508062368457	3
Platelets	0.0024874203759518727	3
AST	0.0020612973989591007	3
BaseExcess	0.0018946532255720416	3
Phosphate	0.0016746994358900484	3
Magnesium	0.0014437092671908882	3
Alkalinephos	0.001112240476351058	3
Hgb	0.0008635556069862563	3
HCO3	0.000713949289905462	3
Chloride	0.0002354462713180743	3
Fibrinogen	0.00012609447905188577	3
Bilirubin	8.724596601310716e-05	6
Gender	0.0	3
TroponinI	0.0	3
Unit2	0.0	3
Unit1	0.0	3

by the authors and are based on the public data from the PhysioNet Challenge 2019.